

Supplementary Material 1: List of specimens used in this study along with information about the collection, scans, feeding ecology and teeth measurements. + indicates the major prey item. Teeth length= L_C (curvature length), mean angle = $D_{C_{mean}}$ (average degree of curvature), max angle = $D_{C_{max}}$ (maximal degree of curvature).

Species	Collection	Diet	Main challenge	Shape	Hardness	Foraging substrate	Scan resolution (μm)	Tooth length (mm)	Mean angle ($^\circ$)	Max angle ($^\circ$)	References [1]
<i>Anilius scytale</i>	A. Herrel	amphisbaenians (+), caecilians, snakes	long	long	hard	ground	1.87	1.926	50.6	244.1	[2,3]
<i>Calabaria reinhardtii</i>	A. Herrel	rodents	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	1.42	1.278	73.4	194.0	[4]
<i>Candoia carinata</i>	A. Herrel	skinks (+), geckos, frogs, mammals	hold	long	hard	branch	2.62	1.800	67.2	169.3	[5]
<i>Eryx jaculus</i>	HUJI 3634	mammals	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	2.00	1.847	84.2	226.5	[6,7]
<i>Boa constrictor</i>	Yoan Eynac	mammals, birds	hold	bulky	soft	branch	7.50	6.678	92.7	291.4	[8]
<i>Corallus annulatus</i>	A. Herrel	mammals, birds	hold	bulky	soft	branch	2.75	1.824	66.1	170.6	[8,9]
<i>Cylindrophis ruffus</i>	Ludovic Faure	caecilians (+), snakes, eels	long	long	hard	ground	1.75	1.369	67.0	143.0	[10–15]
<i>Python regius</i>	A. Herrel	mammals, birds	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	2.15	2.288	49.3	160.2	[16]
<i>Morelia spilota</i>	A. Herrel	generalist but mainly mammals (+)	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	3.37	3.813	72.0	201.5	[17]
<i>Acrochordus javanicus</i>	A. Herrel	eleotrid fish	slippery	long	medium	water	2.27	2.628	71.8	166.9	[18]
<i>Acrochordus granulatus</i>	A. Herrel	eleotrid fish, goby-like fish	slippery	long	medium	water	1.59	1.659	71.3	238.7	[18–21]
<i>Xenodermus javanicus</i>	A. Herrel	frog	bulky	bulky	medium	ground	1.00	0.695	75.8	269.8	[22]
<i>Aplopeltura boa</i>	Karine Falco	snails	slippery	long	soft	branch	1.47	1.248	65.9	243.9	[23–25]

<i>Pareas carinatus</i>	Anthony Herrel	snails	slippery	long	soft	branch	1.22	0.551	89.8	243.1	[26–29]
<i>Eristicophis macmahoni</i>	Latoxan	generalist	hold	na	medium	ground	2.00	1.638	73.7	250.2	[30–33]
<i>Daboia russelii</i>	Venomworld	mammals	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	2.12	2.559	79.7	270.0	[30,33,34]
<i>Causus sp.</i>	Ludovic Faure	amphibians	bulky	bulky	medium	ground	1.59	0.757	86.1	223.0	[33,35,36]
<i>Echis leucogaster</i>	Latoxan	centipedes, scorpions, lizards, mammals	hard	long	hard	ground	1.75	0.593	57.1	153.5	[30,33,37,38]
<i>Bitis gabonica</i>	Latoxan	mammals (+), birds	hold	bulky	soft	ground	3.77	3.156	87.1	279.1	[30,33,39]
<i>Tropidolaemus wagleri</i>	AMNH R50991	mammals	hold	bulky	soft	branch	1.64	1.966	58.5	120.6	[40]
<i>Gloydius halys</i>	Ludovic Faure	mammals	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	1.18	0.889	66.7	201.6	[41]
<i>Bothriechis schlegelii</i>	Venomworld	generalist	hold	na	medium	branch	2.57	2.575	51.6	164.0	[1,42]
<i>Agkistrodon piscivorus</i>	Venomworld	ectotherm generalist	bulky	bulky	medium	ground	2.00	1.656	69.5	158.8	[43–47]
<i>Crotalus adamanteus</i>	A. Herrel	mammals	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	4.25	3.259	68.8	154.8	[48]
<i>Subessor bocourti</i>	A. Herrel	fish: Osphronemidae (+), Pangasidae, Siluridae, Synbranchidae	slippery	bulky	medium	water	2.75	3.051	81.8	331.8	[10,49]
<i>Cantoria violacea</i>	LKC ZRC 2.3317	crustaceans (mostly shrimps)	hard	long	hard	ground	1.00	0.969	72.0	239.2	[49,50]
<i>Fordonia leucobalia</i>	LKC ZRC 2.3294	hard-shelled crustaceans (crabs, lobster)	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.59	0.827	57.3	108.5	[50–52]
<i>Gerarda prevostiana</i>	LKC ZRC 2.3292	crabs	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.00	0.625	64.1	153.4	[49–51]

<i>Homalopsis buccata</i>	A. Herrel	small or long fish (<i>Lebistes reticulatus</i> , <i>Mystus</i> , <i>Monopterus</i> <i>albus</i> , <i>Clarias</i> sp, <i>Puntius binotatus</i>)	slippery	long	medium	water	1.70	2.263	87.1	295.9	[10,49,53]
<i>Malpolon insignitus</i>	HUJI 16560	generalist (mostly mammals)	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	1.81	1.570	57.3	130.5	[54–56]
<i>Atractaspis engaddensis</i>	HUJI 16567	mammals (+), lizards, snakes	bulky	bulky	soft	ground	1.75	0.430	60.1	181.8	[57]
<i>Micrurus psyches</i>	A. Herrel	snakes	long	long	hard	ground	0.97	0.545	68.9	112.8	[58]
<i>Ophiophagus hannah</i>	Latoxan	snakes	long	long	hard	ground	2.27	1.203	64.0	149.7	[59,60]
<i>Dendroaspis viridis</i>	Latoxan	mammals, birds	hold	bulky	soft	branch	1.50	0.987	71.4	281.2	[61]
<i>Naja annulata</i>	Latoxan	fish	slippery	long	medium	water	2.50	2.682	80.3	211.4	[62]
<i>Naja nigricollis</i>	Latoxan	generalist	bulky	na	medium	ground	1.50	1.199	62.4	132.7	[63]
<i>Laticauda colubrina</i>	AMNH R38111	eels	long	long	medium	water	1.06	0.819	112.9	77.3	[52,64–69]
<i>Aipysurus laevis</i>	Latoxan	small or long fish (catfish, small snappers)	slippery	long	medium	water	2.37	2.244	90.8	200.0	[52,66,67,70, 71]
<i>Hydrophis platurus</i>	A. Herrel	small fish	slippery	long	medium	water	1.92	2.347	99.6	280.2	[52,70,72–79]
<i>Grayia ornata</i>	A. Herrel	long fish (siluriform)	slippery	long	medium	branch	1.29	1.559	91.5	276.7	[62,80]
<i>Boiga dendrophila</i>	Latoxan	mammals, birds	hold	bulky	soft	branch	1.83	2.134	63.9	167.1	[81]
<i>Boiga cynodon</i>	Latoxan	generalist	hold	na	medium	branch	2.00	2.034	73.4	129.9	[81]

<i>Dasyeltis scabra</i>	A. Herrel	eggs	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.04	0.572	67.5	248.8	[82]
<i>Dispholidus typus</i>	Latoxan	birds, chameleons, agama, toad	hold	bulky	medium	branch	1.75	1.062	57.7	154.1	[83]
<i>Philothamnus semivariatus</i>	Latoxan	lizards (gecko)	hold	bulky	medium	branch	2.00	0.736	74.0	176.0	[61,80,84]
<i>Eirenis decemlineatus</i>	HUJI 4780	arthropods (orthopterans, insects, spiders, scorpions, centipedes)	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.50	0.495	52.6	98.9	[85,86]
<i>Eirenis lineomaculatus</i>	HUJI 16485	arthropods (orthopterans, centipedes, spiders, scorpions)	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.75	0.475	75.6	158.1	[85,86]
<i>Oxybelis aeneus</i>	A. Herrel	generalist (mostly elongated lizards)	hold	long	medium	branch	1.12	0.998	82.0	209.2	[87,88]
<i>Scolecophis atrocinctus</i>	A. Herrel	centipedes	hard	long	hard	ground	1.01	0.368	64.6	181.8	[89]
<i>Coluber constrictor</i>	AMNH R27367	generalist (snakes (+), elongated lizards...)	long	long	hard	ground	1.25	1.449	64.0	157.1	[90–92]
<i>Stenorrhina degenhardtii</i>	AMNH R38087	arthropods (mostly spiders)	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.59	0.567	56.2	128.0	[93–95]
<i>Gonyosoma boulengeri</i>	A. Herrel	endotherm generalist	hold	bulky	soft	branch	1.50	0.776	83.1	284.0	[96]
<i>Coronella girondica</i>	A. Herrel	elongated lizards (skinks, lacertids, anguis)	long	long	hard	ground	1.40	0.786	63.8	166.7	[97]
<i>Lampropeltis triangulum</i>	AMNH R177123	elongated lizards (+, skinks, <i>Sceloporus</i>), snakes, mammals	long	long	medium	ground	1.22	0.668	46.3	165.7	[98]
<i>Natrix tessellata</i>	HUJI 16537	mostly elongated fish (goby, Cyprinidae...)	slippery	long	medium	water	1.50	1.165	74.5	228.5	[99–101]

<i>Liodytes rigida</i>	AMNH R177031	crayfish	hard	bulky	hard	ground	1.00	0.672	49.9	147.2	[102–105]
<i>Heterodon nasicus</i>	Yoan Eynac	reptiles, toads, eggs, small turtles	bulky	bulky	hard	ground	1.30	1.255	82.3	267.4	[106–109]
<i>Imantodes cenchoa</i>	Vincent Prémel	elongated thin scaled lizards (mostly anoles, +, <i>Gonatodes</i> <i>sp.</i>), amphibians	hold	long	medium	branch	1.00	0.521	87.3	299.3	[3,110]
<i>Atractus flammigerus</i>	MNHN 80-24	earthworms	long	long	soft	ground	1.25	1.107	70.8	193.7	[3,111,112]
<i>Sibon sp.</i>	A. Herrel	amphibian eggs, earthworms, slugs,	slippery	long	soft	branch	1.02	1.058	83.9	236.1	[113,114]
<i>Helicops sp.</i>	A. Herrel	mostly fish (Perciformes, Characiformes, Cyprinodontiformes ...)	slippery	long	medium	water	1.20	1.252	70.6	248.5	[3,115–117]
<i>Siphlophis compressus</i>	Vincent Prémel	mostly elongated thin-scales lizards (anoles, <i>Gonatodes</i>)	long	long	medium	ground	1.59	0.663	62.5	192.4	[1,3]
<i>Clelia clelia</i>	MNHN 79-47	reptiles (mostly snakes +)	long	long	hard	ground	1.40	0.529	52.0	189.5	[1]

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Supplementary Material 2a: Phylogeny of the species included in our sample. Tree pruned from the phylogeny presented in Pyron *et al.* 2014. Species were absent from the phylogeny were replaced by their closest relative in the phylogeny: *Malpolon insignitus* = *Malpolon monspessulanus*, *Atractaspis engaddensis* = *Atractaspis bibronii*, *Scolecophis atrocinctus* = *Tantilla melanocephala*, *Stenorrhina degenhardtii* = *Stenorrhina freminvillei*

Supplementary Material 2b: Snapshots of the 3D reconstructions based on the CTscans for each species along with the phylogeny. Frame color corresponds to prey hardness. This figure shows that dentary teeth are rather similar in shape, although they can vary in size for a few species. Most of the intra-individual variation seen in the snapshot comes from teeth that are being replaced or not fully grown and functional.

Colubridae

Supplementary Material 3: Description of anatomical landmarks placed on the inner (blue) and outer (red) layers of the teeth. Left figure: medial view of the tooth. Right picture: posterior view of the tooth.

LM# Name

- 1 Tip of the pulp cavity
- 2 Most anterior point of the tooth insertion
- 3 Most posterior point of the tooth insertion - according to the orientation with the vascular canal
- 4 Most medial point of the tooth insertion
- 5 Most lateral point of the tooth insertion
- 6 Max. curvature - anterior
- 7 Max. curvature - posterior
- 8 Tip of the tooth
- 9 Most anterior point of the tooth insertion
- 10 Most posterior point of the tooth insertion - according to the orientation with the vascular canal
- 11 Most medial point of the tooth insertion
- 12 Most lateral point of the tooth insertion
- 13 Max. curvature - anterior
- 14 Max. curvature - posterior

Supplementary Material 4: PCA plot showing the repeatability of the anatomical landmark positioning. We landmarked teeth that appear very similar. The plot shows that, despite being similar in shape, repetitions of the same specimen group together together and are separated from the other specimens, based on the 14 anatomical landmarks. Yet, some specimens are close (*Candoia carinata* “C_car” and *Boiga cynodon* “B_cyn”), thus suggesting a need for more accurate shape information using curve and surface semi-landmarks.

Supplementary Material 5: Two examples of curvature digitization using the plugin Kappa in FIJI: *Boa constrictor* (top snapshot), *Eirenis decemlineatus* (bottom snapshot).

Supplementary Material 6: Phylomorphospace of tooth shape variation. Each dot represents one species and is colored according to their main feeding challenge.

Supplementary Material 7: Results of the model fit comparison. Highlighted in grey are models used for post-hoc pairwise tests.

	logLik	residual.pc.no	penalty	AIC
Hardness	14562.49	60	4278	-24846.98
Foraging substrate	14515.25	60	4278	-24752.50
Size + Hardness	14305.41	59	4402	-24208.82
Size + Foraging substrate	14266.06	59	4402	-24130.12
Main challenge	13972.51	58	4526	-23419.02
Size + Main challenge	13719.99	57	4650	-22789.98

Supplementary Material 8: Eigenvalues, proportion of variance and cumulative proportion of variance associated with each Principal Component.

Component	Eigenvalues	Proportion of Variance	Cumulative Proportion
Comp1	0.020781618	0.470	0.470
Comp2	0.005475935	0.124	0.594
Comp3	0.003178485	0.072	0.665
Comp4	0.00268192	0.061	0.726
Comp5	0.001979379	0.045	0.771
Comp6	0.001393383	0.031	0.802
Comp7	0.001170302	0.026	0.829
Comp8	0.001005174	0.023	0.851
Comp9	0.000817548	0.018	0.870
Comp10	0.00078064	0.018	0.888
Comp11	0.000621315	0.014	0.902
Comp12	0.000549496	0.012	0.914
Comp13	0.000452438	0.010	0.924
Comp14	0.000414458	0.009	0.934
Comp15	0.000327358	0.007	0.941
Comp16	0.000270363	0.006	0.947
Comp17	0.000234639	0.005	0.952
Comp18	0.000223911	0.005	0.957
Comp19	0.000186986	0.004	0.962
Comp20	0.000163859	0.004	0.965
Comp21	0.000143923	0.003	0.969
Comp22	0.000137272	0.003	0.972
Comp23	0.000121359	0.003	0.975
Comp24	0.000113178	0.003	0.977
Comp25	8.65E-05	0.002	0.979
Comp26	8.51E-05	0.002	0.981
Comp27	8.20E-05	0.002	0.983
Comp28	7.35E-05	0.002	0.984
Comp29	7.24E-05	0.002	0.986
Comp30	6.03E-05	0.001	0.987
Comp31	4.78E-05	0.001	0.989
Comp32	4.67E-05	0.001	0.990
Comp33	4.03E-05	0.001	0.991
Comp34	3.66E-05	0.001	0.991
Comp35	3.48E-05	0.001	0.992
Comp36	3.30E-05	0.001	0.993
Comp37	3.02E-05	0.001	0.994
Comp38	2.65E-05	0.001	0.994
Comp39	2.36E-05	0.001	0.995
Comp40	2.32E-05	0.001	0.995
Comp41	2.01E-05	0.000	0.996
Comp42	1.91E-05	0.000	0.996
Comp43	1.56E-05	0.000	0.996
Comp44	1.47E-05	0.000	0.997
Comp45	1.41E-05	0.000	0.997
Comp46	1.33E-05	0.000	0.997

Comp47	1.31E-05	0.000	0.998
Comp48	1.17E-05	0.000	0.998
Comp49	1.07E-05	0.000	0.998
Comp50	1.01E-05	0.000	0.998
Comp51	9.28E-06	0.000	0.999
Comp52	8.16E-06	0.000	0.999
Comp53	7.93E-06	0.000	0.999
Comp54	6.49E-06	0.000	0.999
Comp55	6.16E-06	0.000	0.999
Comp56	5.91E-06	0.000	0.999
Comp57	5.41E-06	0.000	1.000
Comp58	4.95E-06	0.000	1.000
Comp59	4.30E-06	0.000	1.000
Comp60	4.01E-06	0.000	1.000
Comp61	3.58E-06	0.000	1.000
Comp62	3.16E-06	0.000	1.000